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Publishing Summary

For manuscripts published from date range October 2020 - October 2025

(2) Zenodo

(1) Jurnal Ekonomi Manajemen Siste...

Publications

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GLOBAL LOGISTICS CORRIDOR INTEGRATION: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW AND SOCIO-TECHNICAL FRAMEWORK

Authors (1): Samuel Darwisman

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From Model to Interpretation: A Comprehensive and Critical Guide to PLS-SEM Implementation in Scientific Research

Authors (1): Samuel Darwisman

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Integrating Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) into Human Resource Management: A Systematic Review, Critical Appraisal, and Framework for the Logistics and Transportation Sector

Authors (4): Samuel Darwisman; Yosef Ricky Simanjuntak ... Aswanti Setyawati
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